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ВІРУС ЕПШТЕЙНА–БАРР: РОЛЬ У ХРОНІЧНИХ ТА ОНКОЛОГІЧНИХ ПРОЦЕСАХ (ОГЛЯД ЛІТЕРАТУРИ)

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EPSTEIN–BARR VIRUS: ROLE IN CHRONIC AND ONCOLOGICAL PROCESSES (LITERATURE REVIEW)

Анотація.

Вірус Епіштейна–Барр (EBV) є одним із найбільш поширених вірусів людини, що інфікує понад 90% дорослого населення у світі. Він належить до родини *Herpesviridae* та характеризується здатністю до довічної персистенції в організмі. Первинна інфекція зазвичай перебігає безсимптомно або у формі інфекційного мононуклеозу, однак у ряді випадків вірус асоціюється з розвитком хронічних патологічних станів. EBV має складні механізми імунної евазії, що дозволяють йому уникати контролю з боку імунної системи. Значну увагу приділяють його ролі в онкогенезі, зокрема у формуванні лімфопроліферативних захворювань та епітеліальних пухлин. Встановлено зв'язок EBV із лімфомою Беркітта, назофарингеальною карциномою та EBV-асоційованим раком шлунка. Хронічна активна EBV-інфекція може призводити до тяжких імунопатологічних уражень. У роботі узагальнено сучасні дані щодо патогенезу, клінічного значення та онкогенного потенціалу EBV.

Abstract.

Epstein–Barr virus (EBV) is one of the most prevalent human viruses, infecting more than 90% of the adult population worldwide. It belongs to the *Herpesviridae* family and is characterized by lifelong persistence in the host. Primary infection is usually asymptomatic or presents as infectious mononucleosis, but in some cases it is associated with chronic pathological conditions. EBV exhibits complex immune evasion mechanisms that allow it to escape host immune surveillance. Particular attention has been paid to its role in oncogenesis, including lymphoproliferative disorders and epithelial malignancies. EBV has been strongly associated with Burkitt lymphoma, nasopharyngeal carcinoma, and EBV-associated gastric cancer. Chronic active EBV infection may lead to severe immunopathological complications. This review summarizes current data on EBV pathogenesis, clinical significance, and oncogenic potential.

Ключові слова: вірус Епіштейна–Барр, EBV, онкогенез, хронічна інфекція, імунна евазія, лімфопроліферація.

Key words: Epstein–Barr virus, EBV, oncogenesis, chronic infection, immune evasion, lymphoproliferation.

The purpose of our scientific work was to analyze modern articles and literary sources, which covered the topic of pathogenetic mechanisms, risk factors, and the role of the Epstein-Barr virus in chronic and oncological processes.

Materials and methods: we conducted a literature review based on articles published in PubMed databases over the past 10 years. Current information on the role of the Epstein-Barr virus in chronic and oncological processes was analyzed.

Discussion results: Epstein–Barr virus (EBV), or human herpesvirus type 4, is one of the most common human pathogens and belongs to the γ -herpesvirinae subfamily. According to modern epidemiological data,

more than 90–95% of the world's adult population is infected with this virus, which indicates its global distribution and high contagiousness [1].

The main way of transmission is contact with the saliva of an infected person, which causes frequent infection in childhood and adolescence [2]. In countries with a high standard of living, the primary infection often manifests as infectious mononucleosis, while in young children it is usually asymptomatic [3].

After entering the body, EBV infects the epithelial cells of the oropharynx and B-lymphocytes using the CD21 receptor, which ensures its tropism to cells of the immune system [4]. An important biological feature of the virus is its ability for lifelong persistence, which is

realized through latent infection in memory B cells [5]. In this state, the viral DNA is stored as an episome, which allows the virus to evade immune surveillance and maintain infection throughout a person's life. Pathogenesis of EBV infection includes two main phases — lytic and latent. In the lytic phase, active replication of the virus occurs with the formation of new virions, which contributes to the spread of infection in the body. Instead, the latent phase is characterized by limited expression of viral genes and the absence of production of viral particles [6]. There are several types of latency that differ in the spectrum of expression of viral proteins, including EBNA and LMP, which play a key role in cell transformation [7].

Mechanisms of immune evasion of EBV attract special attention. The virus is capable of modulating the immune response by reducing the expression of MHC molecules, inhibiting apoptosis, and influencing the production of cytokines [8]. In particular, the LMP1 protein functions as an oncogene, activating NF- κ B signaling pathways, which promotes cell proliferation and survival [9]. These mechanisms allow the virus not only to avoid the immune response, but also to create conditions for the development of chronic pathological processes.

Current research is increasingly paying attention to the role of epigenetic mechanisms in the regulation of EBV-associated cell transformation. It was established that the virus is able to change the DNA methylation of the host cell, which leads to suppression of the expression of tumor suppressor genes and activation of oncogenic signaling pathways. In addition, EBV-induced changes in histone modifications contribute to the stabilization of the latent state of the virus and maintenance of the malignant phenotype of cells. These epigenetic rearrangements are considered as potential therapeutic targets for the development of new strategies for the treatment of EBV-associated neoplasms.

In most immunocompetent individuals, EBV is under the control of cytotoxic T-lymphocytes, but in immunodeficient states this control is disrupted [10]. This can lead to the development of chronic active EBV infection, which is characterized by long-term virus replication, systemic organ damage, and a high risk of death [11].

In addition, EBV is considered as a potential trigger of autoimmune diseases, including systemic lupus erythematosus and multiple sclerosis, which is associated with mechanisms of molecular mimicry and impaired immune tolerance [12].

Thus, EBV is a complex biological agent with unique properties of persistence and immune interaction, which determines its key role in the development of both chronic and oncological processes.

The oncogenic potential of the Epstein-Barr virus is one of the most significant among all known human viruses. According to current estimates, EBV is associated with approximately 1–2% of all malignant neoplasms in the world, which emphasizes its global importance in carcinogenesis [13]. The basis of the oncogenic effect of the virus is the ability to induce the proliferation of infected cells and inhibit apoptosis

mechanisms through the expression of latent viral proteins such as EBNA1, EBNA2 and LMP1 [14].

One of the most studied EBV-associated tumors is Burkitt's lymphoma, which is particularly common in endemic regions of Africa. It is characterized by the translocation of the MYC gene, and EBV acts as a co-factor that contributes to the malignant transformation of B-lymphocytes [15].

Another important example is nasopharyngeal carcinoma, which is closely associated with latent EBV infection and has a high prevalence in Southeast Asian countries. In these tumors, viral proteins contribute to cell proliferation, angiogenesis, and suppression of the immune response [16].

EBV-associated gastric cancer deserves special attention, which accounts for about 10% of all gastric adenocarcinoma cases. In such tumors, the virus induces epigenetic changes, including hypermethylation of tumor suppressor genes, which contributes to carcinogenesis [17]. In addition, EBV plays an important role in the development of post-transplant lymphoproliferative disorders (PTLD), which occur in the background of immunosuppression and are characterized by uncontrolled proliferation of B cells [18].

The molecular mechanisms of EBV-induced oncogenesis include the activation of NF- κ B, JAK/STAT, and PI3K/Akt signaling pathways, leading to cell cycle dysregulation and increased cell survival [19]. The virus is also able to affect the miRNA of the cell, changing the expression of genes involved in the control of growth and differentiation. These changes create a favorable environment for the development of malignant neoplasms.

Current approaches to the diagnosis of EBV infection include serological methods, determination of viral load using PCR, and immunohistochemical detection of viral antigens in tissues. The determination of antibodies to capsid antigen (VCA), nuclear antigen (EBNA) and early antigen (EA) is important, which allows differentiation of the stages of infection [20]. In clinical practice, determination of EBV-DNA in blood plasma is also used as a marker of infection activity and oncological processes.

Recent years have been characterized by the active implementation of liquid biopsy as a promising method of monitoring EBV-associated diseases. Determination of circulating viral DNA in blood plasma allows not only to diagnose an active infection, but also to assess the effectiveness of treatment and the risk of recurrence of the tumor process. It is especially important to use this method in nasopharyngeal carcinoma, where the level of EBV-DNA correlates with the stage of the disease and the prognosis of the patient. Thus, liquid biopsy becomes a key tool of personalized medicine.

Treatment of EBV-associated diseases remains a challenge. For most forms of infection, specific antiviral therapy is limited in its effectiveness, since the latent form of the virus is insensitive to antiviral drugs. In cases of cancer, standard treatments are used, including chemotherapy, radiation therapy, and immunotherapy. Development of vaccines against EBV and targeted therapy aimed at viral proteins are promising directions [13].

A promising direction in the therapy of EBV-associated pathologies is the use of immunotherapeutic approaches, in particular CAR-T cells and immune checkpoint inhibitors. These methods are aimed at restoring an effective cytotoxic response of T-lymphocytes against infected or transformed cells. Preliminary clinical studies demonstrate the potential effectiveness of such strategies in EBV-positive lymphomas, opening new opportunities for the treatment of patients with resistant forms of the disease.

Thus, the Epstein-Barr virus is an important etiological factor in the development of a wide range of oncological diseases, and its complex interactions with the immune system determine both the chronic course of the infection and its malignant potential.

Conclusion: Epstein-Barr virus is one of the key infectious agents that plays an important role in the development of both chronic and oncological processes in humans. Its ability to persist for life, complex mechanisms of immune evasion and influence on cellular signaling pathways lead to a wide range of clinical manifestations. EBV is associated with a number of malignancies, including lymphoproliferative diseases and epithelial tumors, supporting its importance as an oncogenic virus. Despite significant progress in the study of the pathogenesis of EBV infection, the issues of effective prevention and treatment remain relevant. Further research in this area may contribute to the development of new therapeutic approaches and improve the prognosis for patients.

References

1. Young LS, Yap LF, Murray PG. Epstein-Barr virus: more than 50 years old and still providing surprises. *Nat Rev Cancer*. 2016;16(12):789–802.
2. Shannon-Lowe C, Rickinson AB, Bell AI. Epstein-Barr virus-associated lymphomas. *Philos Trans R Soc B*. 2017;372(1732):20160271.
3. Kimura H, Cohen JI. Chronic active Epstein-Barr virus disease. *Front Immunol*. 2017;8:1867.
4. Tsao SW, Tsang CM, Lo KW. Epstein-Barr virus infection and nasopharyngeal carcinoma. *Philos Trans R Soc B*. 2017;372(1732):20160270.
5. Smatti MK, Al-Sadeq DW, Ali NH, et al. Epstein-Barr virus epidemiology, serology, and genetic variability. *Infect Genet Evol*. 2018;57:238–249.

6. Farrell PJ. Epstein-Barr virus and cancer. *Annu Rev Pathol*. 2019;14:29–53.

7. Münz C. Latency and lytic replication in Epstein-Barr virus-associated oncogenesis. *Nat Rev Microbiol*. 2019;17(11):691–700.

8. Shannon-Lowe C, Rickinson AB. The global landscape of EBV-associated tumors. *Front Oncol*. 2019;9:713.

9. Zhang Y, Dai Y, Zheng T, et al. Epstein-Barr virus and cancer: molecular mechanisms and therapeutic strategies. *Signal Transduct Target Ther*. 2021;6:15.

10. Bjornevik K, Cortese M, Healy BC, et al. Epstein-Barr virus and multiple sclerosis. *Science*. 2022;375(6578):296–301.

11. Tangye SG, Palendira U, Edwards ESJ. Human immunity against EBV. *J Exp Med*. 2017;214(2):269–283.

12. Taylor GS, Long HM, Brooks JM, et al. Immunology of Epstein-Barr virus infection. *Annu Rev Immunol*. 2015;33:787–821.

13. Dunmire SK, Verghese PS, Balfour HH Jr. Primary Epstein-Barr virus infection. *J Clin Virol*. 2018;102:84–92.

14. Khan G, Hashim MJ. Global burden of EBV-associated malignancies. *Pathogens*. 2020;9(1):38.

15. Murphy G, Pfeiffer R, Camargo MC, Rabkin CS. EBV-positive gastric cancer meta-analysis. *Gastroenterology*. 2019;156(3):824–833.

16. Dunleavy K, Tay K, Wilson WH. EBV-positive lymphoproliferative disorders. *Blood*. 2020;136(8):915–928.

17. Cohen JI. Epstein-Barr virus infection and associated lymphoproliferative disorders. *Lancet*. 2023;402(10409):101–114.

18. Crawford DH, Swerdlow AJ. Epstein-Barr virus and oncogenesis. *Curr Opin Virol*. 2016;20:76–82.

19. Cohen JI. Epstein-Barr virus vaccines and immunotherapy strategies. *Clin Transl Immunology*. 2020;9(7):e1139.

20. Delecluse HJ, Feederle R, O'Sullivan B, Taniere P. Epstein-Barr virus-associated malignancies. *Virus Res*. 2017;227:45–50.